

**NIGERIAN COMIC ARTS: HYPOTHETISING TEMPORAL
SOCIAL CHANGE AND WORD CHOICES IN COMEDIES OF
NIGERIAN SOUTH**

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Abstract

This study is a critical exploration of the humour sub-industry in Nigeria with purposive emphasis on the Southern Nigeria humour artistry. Substantial research exists on the Nigerian film industry, the Nollywood, yet equal level, of attention is yet to be paid to the humour rendition in digital/virtual form despite the critical roles humour plays in Nigerian social system. The study has been carried out on Hedonist theoretical framework. The audio-video data for analysis were collected with consideration for temporal balance, age, as well as geo-political representation. The study notes that temporal change in Nigerian political

landscape and digital revolution dictated the contents and modes of humour deliveries in Nigeria. Military regimes made earlier humorist such as Baba Sala concentrated on human-angle themes. However, Nigeria's return to democracy in 1999, and social media advancement with all its ubiquitous and global accessibility aided the emergence and explosion of political comedy school as a mode humour expression. This is the standup comic artistry with emphasis on its political ramification. The political standup comedians in Nigeria such as I Go Die, MC Monica, and Sarki Dariya, make their comedies serve as voicing of people's displeasure with the social decline in the country. They make the language of expression stylistically strategic as the diction of Nigerian standup political comedies is essentially acerbic and dominantly consists of expletives. The efforts of these political comedians cannot yet be seen as having achieved their goal of social change as hardship persists in the country. However, temporality and social media have gone a long way in shaping the nature of the humour sub-industry in Nigerian south.

Keywords: Southern Nigeria, Nigerian standup comedy, Humour, Baba Sala, Word choice

Introduction

The comedy industry in Nigeria is a unit of the larger film industry of the country. It should be stated that the comedy industry did not strategically start as such but it is currently so. It is a vibrant sub-industry of the film industry in Nigeria. However, this study is concerned with the section of the Nigeria, the Southern part of the country. This comprises Southwest, Southeast, and Southsouth regions of the country. The whole of the country is not covered because of the volume of data to be analysed which may exceed the volume limit of a typical study. The remaining parts of Nigeria have been designated for further study. The Southwest of Nigeria can be seen as the headquarters of comedy in Nigeria. This is not in terms of how funny the comedies are or the creative potential of the comic personalities. It is, however, in terms of the concentration of the comic professionals in Lagos because of the concepts of the Lagos Factor. The Lagos Factor is the career growth of Nigerians comedians.

The Lagos Factor is conceptualized as the glitz, cosmopolitanism, heterogeneity, massive wealth, high population, modern infrastructures and the presence of the

elite to mention some of the constituents of the Lagos factors. As a result of these factors, the comedy sub-industry in Southwest Nigeria is a viable bloc in Nigerian entertainment industry. Its viability further reflects in the economic roles it performs. It also manifests in the cultural roles it performs in the Nigeria as whole, as it is part of the film industry in the country. We also see it in the political significance of the comedy sub-industry in Southwest Nigeria. At this juncture, it is significant to state that the comedy unit of the Nigerian film industry has a deep history. This is due to the constantly-shifting social system of Nigeria. The advent of the millennium has also played crucial roles in the making and shaping of the comedy industry in Southern Nigeria. The focus of this study is to examine the influence of society on the contents and tools of creativity in Southern Nigerian comic works. The study also, in reverse complementary order, investigates the roles, significance, and impacts of the comic industry in Southern Nigeria on the society.

Methodological Approaches to the Study

This study is conceived to be qualitative, by which propositions, hypotheses, and conclusions in the paper are based on rationalisation of thoughts, citing contents for proof, logic and acceptability. In addition to this, the author employed Vincent van Gogh's conception of artistic Expressionism as well as Émile Durkheim's theory of Functionalism which emphasises the heuristic fusion of curatives contents and social progression as guiding theories. Furthermore, the research is both diachronic and synchronic in conception. This is to reflect the historical dimension and the relevance of illustrating the present in the work. Specific humour professionals and their comic works are selected and analysed for tangible illustrations. These selections are predicated on certain criteria, which include the street, populism, and national connection and relevance of the comic actors. The comic actors are also selected with conscious consideration for ethnic nationalities of the comedians. This becomes very important because Southern Nigeria comprises many ethnicities such as Igbo people, the Yoruba, Edo people, and the Niger-Deltans. The Southwest through Lagos is just their concentrations because of the prosperity of Lagos. The selections of the illustrative comic works were based on the grossing qualities of the works as well as the view performances and comments vibrancy of the works online.

The Southern Nigeria and the Significance of Southwest Nigeria

In the geo-political delineation of Nigeria, is one of the two broad blocs. It comprises three geo-political zones including Southwest, Southeast, and South-south of the country. The Southwest Nigeria is originally populated by the aboriginal Yoruba people; the Southeast is home to the indigenous Igbo people, while the South-south is the original home of the minority ethnic peoples of Nigeria, including the Edo and, to mention a few, the Itsekiri. However, the Lagos Factor has motivated mass influx indigenes of the Southeast and South-south regions into Southwest especially into Lagos. Lagos is an economically viable city in Nigeria, indeed, in the larger Africa (Koko and Bello, 2023). This accounts for the reasons why and initiatives, reality shows or industry needs the Lagos influence to be top-notched. It is in line with this situation that the Southwest Nigeria can be seen as the headquarters of the comedy industry. There is higher concentration of internationally-exposed comedians from the diverse ethnic groups in Lagos, Southwest. There is also high concentration of organisers of international Comedy Shows such as Ali Baba, AY Show, and Bovi, to mention a few. In same vein, many of the A-List non-Yoruba comic celebrities have been used to the social and cultural life of the Yoruba, especially in systematic/creative use of the Yoruba language. This is the language of the Yoruba in Southwest. The acculturation of the comedy celebrities is an additional signifier of the significance of Southwest in the film industry in Nigeria.

Temporality and the Shifting Forms of Nigerian Comedies: the Context of Digital Modernity and Autarchy

The nature and contents of comic creativities in Nigeria diverge from time to time. Two major factors could be attributed to this. These include temporality and totalitarianism in which case the millennium is a determining central factor. The millennium is significant because it was just the time of Nigeria's return to democratic governance in 1999. Prior to the advent of the millennium in the year 2000/2001, Nigerians were ruled by the military and Military administrations in Nigeria were marked by terror noted in corruption, press gagging, and economic decline (Adu and Aluko, 2023). These two temporal scenarios which the Millennium stands at the center of, creates the pre-Millennial and Millennial

social systems and eras in Nigeria. This affected the contents and nature of Nigerian comedies and the system of delivering the comic contents to the public.

The pre-millennial period in Nigeria was marked by military regimes of General Mohammedu Buhari, General Ibrahim Gbadamosi Babangida, General Sani Abacha and General Abdulsalam Abubakar. These regimes, being military regimes, were characterised by terror such as breach of fundamental human rights (Adeakin, 2016). Due to this characteristic of the military, comedic contents were on small talks, human angles as they pertained to the subalterns. This characterised the comedies of such pioneers such as Baba Sala, Baba Mero, Baba Suwe, Gbenga Adeboye, Sam Loco Efe, Nkem Owoh and so on.

The millennial age in Nigeria witnessed two major circumstances which include democratic governance and digital modernity through constant electoral exercises and the exposure to cyber-life, respectively. However, the democratic experience was unpleasant to the Nigerian civil society. This is because since 1999, when Nigerian to the democratic mode of government, the democratic experiment in the country has witnessed electoral violence and bad Governance as marked by financial corruption, nepotism, and electoral rigging noted in early 2000s (Omotola, 2010), and forth. There was mistrust between the electorate and the government as a result. The digital age however enlightened the youth who had access to the Western civilization. Those who had gift of wit made careers in stand-up comedy. They took advantage of the YouTube platform prior to the advent of other social media platforms such as, WhatsApp, X and to mention a few TikTok. The social media platforms have enabled them globalise their humour careers. It needs to be stated that such factors as the liberality of the democratic governance, digital modernity, and the non-physical presence of social media humour creators have made the Nigerian humorists from South of Nigeria address politically sensitive humour. This makes the humor contents of the millennial era different from the early-day pre-millennial humor, which was essentially civil and humanist. Specific illustrations are thus interrogated forth.

Illustrative Analyses of Humour Aesthetics in Southern-Nigeria Comedies

The ultimate essence of humor is the evocation of laughter in the people. To achieve the critical task, comedians in Southern Nigeria have designed and

adopted different creativities. The goal at this juncture of the study is to analyze specific comic works from Southern Nigeria in order to determine comic resources as aesthetics in the works.

The Human-angle Comedies

The first to consider in this category is Baba Sala's comedies. Baba Sala, (1936-2018), whose real name was Moses Olaiya, was an iconic comedian in Southern Nigeria. He was prolific in the production of comic works. His works included *Orun Mooru, Aare Agbaye, Mosebolatan, Agba Man*. In addition to these films, he was also active on radio and television. He was a comic superstar and legend. Indeed, Angoye (2018) describes Moses Olaiya as 'the father of Nigerian comedy'. What can be deduced from this adulation is that Baba Sala substantially fulfilled the core essence of comedy; that is hilarity. To achieve substantial hilarity in his works, Baba Sala employed some strategies and tools of comic aesthetics. This is within the framework of Appearance, Thought, and Language deployment. These frameworks are designed within the social contexts and interpretation as illustrated in some of his works. Characteristically, Baba Sala's appearance was a reflection of societal influences.

His heydays were the time of the wake of colonial characteristics. Such included the pose of the typical Englishman which was a mark of civilisation in Nigeria at the time. Baba Sala represented this with his black round hat and the protruding tobacco stick, hanging on his lips. This is, however, scuttled by the oversized lens-less spectacles. This combination gives a confused impression as the hat and tobacco sticks give an impression of a civilised English gentleman. However, the oversized lens-less spectacle and overflowing local apparel give an impression of an unschooled personality. This is because of the collision of the Western gears and the overflowing local wears. The hilarity created reaches its peak when Baba Sala calls other cast, illiterate. This appearance description for hilarity purpose is noted in his cover picture in the audio tape titled 'Baba Sala - Agbongbotan Ede Audio' available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6nDswCwuKOs&t=76s>.

Additionally, Baba Sala's tools of humour also included make-believe of ignorance. This is in the Thought Formwork itemised above. In this framework for humor construction, foolery is exhibited for mockery. This is overt in the

YouTube video titled ‘Baba Sala Ja si’(‘Baba Sala is Civilised’) available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=efTLQDp-qaQ>. Here Baba Sala is seen returning home unexpectedly contrary to initial travel plans only to catch his daughter with a Sugar Daddy in his sitting room. The Sugar Daddy quickly contrives a classmate relationship in which case the Sugar Daddy is solving a mathematical equation for the daughter. The daughter buys this and tells her father stating ‘Ah, daddy welcome... he is the Senior Boy of our school. It is what I do not understand at school that he is explaining to me at home’. Ignorance is exhibited by the father when he asks for the section of the boys in a girls-only school. This is why his daughter refers to him as *oponu dudu*(a black fool). At this juncture, members of the audience are amused.

However, the common sense of the father saves him from sustained ridicules he is puzzled wondering how an older man with heavy mustache would be in high school. However, before the activation of common sense, hilarity, the critical essence, has been achieved in the laughter of the audience. This makes the work a successful comedy. In the context of ignorance and illiteracy in the context of language, furthermore, when the sugar daddy tells the father that he is teaching his daughter *mathematics*, ignorance is feigned when Baba Sala screams thus ‘You are teaching my child *magic*’. This is similar to the father’s misconstruing *warn* with *warm* at the point in the video when he wishes to let the trespasser-sugar daddy leave, saying ‘I *warm* you with this one case’. These semantic infractions are intended for the hilarity of the educated upper-class audience who are amused by the inability of the comedian to differentiate between the words in a gradually but progressively westernised Nigerian society at the time in the 1970s.

The Nature of Nkem Owoh’s Comic Aesthetics

Another personality in the human-angle humour industry in Nigeria is Nkem Owoh. The choice of Owoh is for the purpose of symbolic illustration of the other iconic comic professionals in his era. This is the era that transcends the pre-millennial era into the millennium. Owoh’s comic artistry is remarkable because it encapsulates imaginative tools in the form of rhetorical instruments. These tools constitute his humorous gift of the gab. The tools are, at this juncture of the study, appraised in the context of the eponymous film *Atinga* available at

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PloiZCVH8_dOECsHGKQuYFf6hr3R19nfVZ. In this brand of comedy aesthetics, Owoh focuses on village life playing the village fools in the rustic setting. In Atinga, Owoh is seen seated on a hip of sand with Amaka and a rich man drives past. The rich man stops his car after spotting Amaka, the village beauty. He signals to her to come, but Atinga antagonises out of jealousy, and when the rich man needs hands to push his car, Atinga sabotages the pushing by pulling having set a barrier against the pushing.

There was also the rejection of including other men in pushing the car dysfunctional car. This comedy is about the subaltern and the village life. Owoh also sets his comedy around the human-angle experiences in yet another comedy *Money Miss Road* available at [https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jVFE99_fp78\\$list=PLoiZOVH8_dOECsHGQuYFf6hr3r19NFuz&index=z](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jVFE99_fp78$list=PLoiZOVH8_dOECsHGQuYFf6hr3r19NFuz&index=z). In this comedy, Owoh explores the McGuffin of rustic ignorance as typified in the perception that a man who lives in the village is often deceived by their educated children. In this instance, a daughter submits a list of books purportedly prescribed by the university she is attending stating, for example, that GRAMMATICALLY costs #8, 000. It takes the intervention of an educated village school girl to decode that GRAMMATICALLY cannot be purchased. And when he continues his journey on his bicycle on a lonely ploughed village road, his ignorance becomes palpable to the effect of hilarity on the audience.

Political Comedies

In the context of this study, political comedies are the hilarious creative artistry that satirises the inadequacies of the political leaders, and in Nigeria, in this particular context, over the years. Political comedy has the potential to influence government decisions and policies for social change (Holm, 2026). As a result of this political comedy which is essentially visible digitally especially on social media with the capabilities of effecting social and political reforms as they comic products serve as social commentaries (Ude et al, 2025). There are many of these comic creativities in the Nigerian creative industry. However, there are conditions that surround this type of comic genre. This is because it is only the standup comedy genre that is essentially political as the social signification of its hilarity.

This type of comic creativity is currently being practised by a set of southern comic actors.

It should be stated that these comic actors are different from the Nollywood comedians. The Nollywood comedians are politically aligned (Imo, 2022; Nwokedi, et al, 2026), and they hardly make profound political statements in respect of protest against administrative laxities of the government. To this end, the comedians whose works are to be studied in this study are the standup comedians who are a new breed of the players in the humour industry in Nigeria who are heralded by the advent of social media. The major characteristics of the southern Nigerian comic acts include bravery, boldness, tact, intelligence, creativity, dynamism, realism, and sensation. Some of these standup comedies are analysed as follows.

I Go Die and his Leadership Culpability Theory for Africa's Decline

I Go Die is a major player in the standup comic industry in Nigeria. He is one of the pioneers of the standup comic genre in Nigeria. I Go Die's model of standup comedy is mimetic and political. Since the political essence of Nigerian standup comedy is the crux at this juncture of this study, the instance of I Go Die's comedy is explored. And this is seen in his rendition in a video titled "12 Solid Nigerian standup comedians in one Night at Darkin Dariya Multiple Laffs" as available at <https://www.youtube/watch?v=ecYyUJ1UaDY>. As I GO Die declares in his rendition: "The only thing killing Africa is bad leadership. We don't have good leaders. Bad leaders, they are the ones killing this country. Every Nigerian's brain has been customised. All our heads are programmed ..."

In this comment by I Go Die, it is conspicuous that the conception of the comedian is that political leaders in Africa have deployed the resources available to them to control the people, the citizens, who constitute the electorate. One may wonder how the comedian can argue the validity of this assertion. At this juncture, it should be averred that the goal is not to debate the validity or veracity of the comedian's position. Rather, it is germane to explore how political leaders in Africa perpetrate the vice especially Nigeria where electoral system is merchandised (Owasa, 2014; Arthur, 2021) that I Go Die alleges in the excerpt. Therefore, it is believed in the study that governments in Africa often programme

the psychology and conscience of the people with money. This is possible because there is massive poverty in Africa (Becker, 2024).

MC Monica is another comic stalwart in Nigeria who injects political material in his comic contents. Evidence of this abounds in his comic productions as can be gleaned from his comments in the video titled “12 Solid Nigerian standup comedians in one Night at Darkin Dariya Multiple Laffs’ as available at <https://www.youtube/watch?v=ecYyUJ1UaDY>. In this work, MC Monica retorts:

The country where we all are confused; the first political tenure has not ended, politicians have started campaigning for 2027. In this difficult time ...Nigeria will soon expire, on Thursday. You can see they deceived us... If you have access to public funds, embezzle them. There is no conscience in Nigeria. Everyone is stealing...

It is obvious in this excerpt that MC Monica is satirising the social menace of misplaced priorities of Nigerian politicians, avarice and recklessness. In the same vein, Sarki Dariya, a vibrant comic talent from the northern part of Nigeria, is also political in his standup skits. This can be gleaned in the comic compilation with the title “12 Solid Nigerian standup comedians in one Night at Darkin Dariya Multiple Laffs’ as available at <https://www.youtube/watch?v=ecYyUJ1UaDY>. Here, Sarkin Dariya is seen asserting thus:

We take too many risks in this country. You know why? We talk about Tinubu and you laugh... Tinubu is a person who will wake up one day and sell this country to Burkina Faso saying “Traore I want to sell this country”... How many of you remember that video when Peter Obi and Tinubu met in Rome at the inauguration of the new Pope... Tinubu said to Peter Obi “ Peter, you came” ... Well, are you

contesting? You said I stole your mandate ...
Well, I will steal it again”...

As can be deduced in this excerpt, there are two critical social vices which Sarkin Dariya satirises in this excerpt. They include unbridled avaricious merchandise and electoral robbery. Tinubu is the current president of Nigeria while Obi was also a candidate in the presidential elections that brought the current president to power in 2023. It was generally believed in the opposition camp that the election was rigged (Mene, 2024). This despicable democratic vice is what the comedian is subjected to mockery in the excerpt.

This political twist to the humour career of these standup comic acts in Nigeria is permissible because of democratic liberalism as the core political philosophy being practiced in Nigeria today. It is this that the standup comics have leveraged on. It would be noted that comic artistry prior to Nigeria’s return to democracy in 1999, a period marked by military highhandedness, was civil and humanist, not political. To this end, two major social phenomena have enabled the political contents of Nigerian standup comic artistry, and these are the evolution of social media technologies and democracy. The former provides the pivotal digital access while the later enables human and social liberalism and liberty, though it has been alleged that the democratic dispensation in Africa is also highhanded.

The Choice of Words of the Standup Comedians

The choice of words of these comedians is not random; they are actually strategic, goal-oriented, and planned. A choice of words is the preferred kind of words and how the words are used by a writer for strategic meanings in different audience contexts (Lems, 2023, Ahmed, 2025, and Kobuljonova and Dilshodjon, 2024). Each of the words these comedians used conveys a conscious meaning. Some of these strategic words are analysed at this juncture of the study. First of all, it needs to be restated that these comedians actually aim at convey a message of displeasure and agony across to the government. The words that they use actually point to the articulation of this intentional aims of the human-angle and political standup comedians. This is as explained thus. To start with, it needs to be stated that the aim of all of these comedians as a bloc of humour artist is hilarity. The words they have selected signify this bottom line. But there are peculiarities. For

example, the peculiarity of the human-angle comedians is the hedonistic pleasure of the ordinary people.

However, that of the political comedians is essentially acerbic. The choice of words, for example, of the humour artist in this study affirms that there are anomie, lack, anger, frustration, hopelessness and general decline in Nigeria as a whole. For example, “killing Africa” and “killing the country” are extracted from I Go Die’s comments, “confused”, “deceive”, “embezzle”, and “everyone is stealing” are culled from MC Monica’s words, while “we are at risks”, “sell the country” and “stole” are culled from Sarkin Dariya’s humorous expressions. When these words are critically examined, these words suggest mortality, fear, lack, apprehension, insecurity, and general anomie. These are the true reflections of the actual social situations in the country. The words are, therefore, not accidental.

They are purposive, and driven to reflect the candid no hold barred social realities of Nigeria plagued with unbridled killings, food insecurity, electoral fraud, and, to mention a few, embezzlements in government. All of these signal a society enmeshed in social disorder. These are what the standup comedians intended to find strategic solutions to. However, if the comedians lay claims to the existence of these vices in the country without them exhibit them, there will be no sense of reality, actuality, and conviction. This is what the comedians achieved with their choice of words as analysed in the study. The portrayal of the social situations in Nigeria by these comedians as vividly as they have done has raised the question of how efficient their word-choice strategies have been. That is has the Nigerian social situations changed as a result of these efforts? The despicable social situations in Nigeria have not changed especially because the democratic governance in Nigeria is intolerant of opposition (Akindele et al, 2009).

The Social Functionality of the Nigerian Humour: A Critical Perspective

Humour performs social functions in Southern Nigeria as indeed, it does in the rest of Nigeria. It should be reiterated that Nigeria social system is a tense social system. It has been such a system characterised by lack, poverty, press gagging, financial recklessness in government, illiteracy, food scarcity as well as deficit of infrastructural facilities. These and many other vices have resulted in palpable

tensions in Nigeria, particularly in the Southern part of Nigeria being the center of this discourse. As a result of this, Southern Nigerians seek and find answer in humour as it performs a number of social functions in different ramifications. First of all, the human angle humour help the people therapeutically as the people regale the hilarious substances in the comic compositions. The humorous contents relieve the tensions in the people as they listen or watch the comic productions. This helps to douse, if not permanently surmount, the tensions in the Nigeria.

In the same vein, the political dimension to the standup comedies by standup comedians in Southern Nigeria, functions as the voice of the people. It should be stated that most Nigerian citizens do not voice out their displeasure over the maladministration in the country. This is essentially because Nigerian democracy is despotic (Madueke and Enyiazu, 2025). They are afraid to come in the open to vent their anger for government to hear their complaints. The comedians, however, do so. They hide behind cover of comic innocence and comic privilege. However, in spite of the fact that the comedians hide behind the cover of comic privilege, the truth in their contents is conveyed to the government, though government often dispels the venting of such citizens' displeasure. Despite this situation, however, it is hoped for that someday, government will listen to the comedians and ensure good governance as the crux of their comic satires.

Conclusion

Comedy sub-industry in Southern Nigeria is conditioned by temporality and digital revolution. The temporal factor was conditioned by the change in the governance and political model in the country. The military regimes in Nigeria prevented comic acts at the time from seeking to reform the society through comic allusions. This is because of the totalitarian tendencies in military reigns. The outcome of the military highhandedness was the resort of the comedians at the time such as Baba Sala in the case of Southwest Nigeria and Nkem Owoh to human-angle comic genre. There was the emergence of a number of firebrand comedians who sprang up at the return of Nigeria to democracy in 1999. These vibrant comedians took advantage of the liberal tendencies of democratic principles by which criticism is tolerated, to deploy comedy in drawing attention of government to social ills and improprieties in the entirety of Nigeria. These

Southern Nigerian comedians are strategic in their word usage as an intentional means of depicting the society the way it is to the global society.

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